

Example specimen citation

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<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4034747>

A simple example of different types of physical and digital specimen citation.

Islam, Sharif (2020): Example specimen citation

doi: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4034747>, [supplementary data: nsid:

<https://hdl.handle.net/20.5000.1025/c2618387bb0932270617>]/[<https://doi.org/20.5000.1025/c2618387bb0932270617>]

Physical Specimen

A [2012 blog post](#) (“*How and why to cite museum specimens in research*”) mentions the following:

“*What is citation? A citation is when a specific museum specimen is mentioned in a paper and can be for a number of reasons. In taxonomic work, it may be that the specimen(s) is the basis for a new species and the characters shown by individual museum specimens define that group. It may be that molecular samples taken from museum specimens have been analysed to work out the relationships or evolution of entire groups of organismal life. It can also be that individual specimen shows something completely unique, be it a bizarre colour variant, evidence of behaviour, pathology or extreme size. Citing a specimen should be as formal as referencing previous literature and should point future workers to the exact objects that were examined so that they can be rechecked or analysed. Normally this is a reference to the specimen’s **museum** or **accession number**.*”

CETAF Stable identifier

Table format

Species	Collector Name and No	HTTP URI
<i>D. macrocarpa</i>	Goldsmith, M. 207	http://data.rbge.org.uk/herb/E00435912
<i>D. macrocarpa</i>	Harris, D.J. 5093	http://data.rbge.org.uk/herb/E00435914
<i>D. viridiflora</i>	Harris, D.J. 6016	http://data.rbge.org.uk/herb/E00435919

Example Digital Specimen citation (this is still work in progress)

This example research project ‘X’ used *Pygmaepterys pointieri* voucher MNHN-IM-2013-7767 and digital specimen (NSId:

<https://hdl.handle.net/20.5000.1025/c2618387bb0932270617>).

Table format

Species Name	Physical SpecimenID	HTTP URI	NSId (Natural Science Identifier)
<i>Pygmaepterys pointieri</i>	MNHN-IM-2013-7767	http://coldb.mnhn.fr/catalognumber/mnhn/im/2013-7767	https://hdl.handle.net/20.5000.1025/c2618387bb0932270617 https://doi.org/20.5000.1025/c2618387bb0932270617